

D.0.6 Minutes of the closing meeting 2022

WP0 Project coordination

Responsible Partner: DTU

Contributing partners: ANSES, SSI, UCM, INRA, IP, APHA, ISS, IZSAM, IZSLER, RIVM, WBVR, PIWET, SLV, FOHM, SVA, Finnish Food Authority

GENERAL INFORMATION

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European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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Author	Susanne Karlsmose Pedersen, DTU and Malgorzata Ligowska-Marzeta, SSI		
Other contributors	WP leaders (DTU, SSI, ANSES, IP)		
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Dissemination	<p>Save date: 21-Dec-22</p> <p>This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):</p> <p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>		

MINTUES - EJP CARE CLOSING MEETING 2022

Participants

EJP CARE closing meeting minutes

Date: 21-22.09.2022

Representatives from the following institutions participated at the meeting (25 attendees):

National Food Institute-DTU (EURL-AR) (Denmark), State Serum Institute (Denmark), Istituto Superiore di Sanità (EURL STEC) (Italy), Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Lombardia e dell'Emilia Romagna (IZSLER) (Italy), National Institute for Public Health and Environment (RIVM) (EURL SALM) (the Netherlands), WUR WBVR (the Netherlands), National Veterinary Institute (SVA, EURL CAMP) (Sweden), Swedish National Food Agency (Sweden), National Veterinary Research Institute, Puławy (NVRI) (Poland), VISAVET – UCM (Spain), ANSES (France), Institut Pasteur (France), French National Institute for Agricultural Research (France), Finnish Food Authority, Finland

Meeting notes: [Susanne Karlsrose Pedersen and Malgorzata Ligowska-Marzeta](#)

21 September 2022 – Day 1

Rene Hendriksen, DTU, opened the 1½-days meeting by welcoming the meeting participants followed by a short introduction of the participants and an introduction to the meeting.

During the meeting, each of the four WP leads would present the progress and outcomes of the WP and discuss sustainability, on the first day focusing at WP 1 and WP 2/3.

WP1 targets, accomplishments and sustainability, Jeppe Boel

WP1-T1 'Mapping of existing and proposals for new PT schemes' (work by Lucas Wijnands) has been finalized.

WP1-T2 where cross sectorial pilot PT's, of which three have been provided to the EJP CARE project members:

- WP1-T2-ST1 'Pilot PT on isolation/detection of pathogens'
- WP1-T2-ST2 'Pilot PT on typing/characterization including WGS'
- WP1-T2-ST3 'Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data'

Elina Lahti (SVA) coordinated the pilot PT on isolation/detection of pathogens and stressed that the keyword is cross sectorial. To our knowledge a cross sectorial PT (or EQA) had not been done before and caused some considerations as the aim for laboratories in the public health sector compared to the food/veterinary sector in relation to isolating/detecting pathogens. The conclusion was that future PT's of this type should maybe be divided into a 'detection component' and a 'culture component'. It was agreed that it would be relevant to continue setting up this type of PT, also, and was discussed which laboratory might be able to provide a PT of this type. Rene suggested that we move forward with preparing a one-pager describing the idea of setting up this kind of PT and to use this for raising awareness of PT's aiming to offer such PT's for relevant laboratories to allow them to use them to quality assure the surveillance data they provide. The one-pager could be forwarded to international collaborators, for example ECDC/WHO/FAO/EURL networks.

Susanne Karlsmose Pedersen (DTU Food) coordinated the 'pilot PT on typing/characterization including WGS' and her colleagues, Lauge and Athina, presented the outcomes of the PT. Both the sequences quality of the submitted FASTA files and the results submissions related to the participants' analysis of the obtained sequences were evaluated and detailed results and discussions are available in the pilot PT report. The workshop participants discussed the quality parameters applied for the sequence analysis and it was agreed that it would be highly relevant to continue this type of PT. Currently, within EU, funding allows the EURL-AR to offer it annually to laboratories in the EURL-AR network.

Jeppe Boel (SSI) coordinated the 'pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data' and concluded that both SNP-based and allele-based methods were working well. Within EU, clustering PT's have been provided from the EURL VTEC, EURL Campy and from ECDC.

Additional ongoing activities in WP1 include development of a 'Guidance document for cross sectorial proficiency testing' and 'SOPs for specific WGS proficiency testing distributions'.

In conclusion it was discussed how to move forward and what might need to be done to promote the setup of relevant PT's. The different sectors have different needs and discussions around this need to continue to ensure that the right decision is reached.

General comment on DMP (Mia Torpdahl)

The Data Management Plan (DMP) must present concrete dataset that has been created in this project. This is related to data, including sequences and MALDI-TOF results.

The DMP needs to be updated regularly.

WP2/3 targets, accomplishments and sustainability

For WP 2, WP lead Olivier Chesneau (IP) updated on the transfer of data/strains to the BRC's. In brief, the reference material providers sign an MDA, send the reference material to one of the three BRC's, who upon request, send reference material to users (after signature of an MTA).

Each MDA/MTA describes the strains, i.e., for each deposit, a new MDA/MTA is required.

It was discussed that the current list of strains does not give an exact picture of the European food safety pathogen risks, and that this should maybe be added as a disclaimer when the CARE collection is published.

A gap analysis is planned allowing experts to examine the current list of strains with the aim to make the CARE collection more complete.

For WP 3, WP lead Michel-Yves Mistou (INRAE) supplemented with details related to the Biolomics database which holds data on the reference material that is available for the scientific community to look into and request. It was discussed whether the expert groups should be encouraged to continue with defined roles. It was concluded that an official curator of the reference material was beyond the scope of the EJP CARE project.

WP4 targets, accomplishments and sustainability, Laurent Guillier

WP4 aimed to investigate and benchmark the availability and quality of the existing (meta-)data relevant for risk assessment and has been working to harmonize data with the purpose to increase the accessibility and for higher comparability. And aims to avoid duplication!

Moreover, WP4 has been collaborating with the other EJP CARE WP's to define strain selection strategies for phenotypic or genomics studies as well as working on an R-tool for sampling strains based on metadata in a One Health context.

Laurent summarized the activities and outcomes of the WP as follows:

Survey for identification of metadata from QMRA studies

- a. To assess the availability and quality of data
- b. Sphinx online software
- c. Survey conducted from September 2020 to March 2021
- d. 18 QMRA studies identified from 6 organisations

Survey findings:

- Poultry and pork are the main product
- Listeria is the main hazard
- Importance of starting point and end point (consumer stage) in risk assessment

Origins of data identified:

- From literature (88%)
- Produced by the risk assessor/organization (72%)
- Data from a scientific network (18%)
- 16 QMRA published

Feedback to the survey was requested among participants, only 3 responses received.

Positive points identified:

- Multiple QMRA dedicated to several sectors and microbiological hazards identified
- Part of data is publicly available

Negative points identified:

- Few QMRA conducted in the last 5 years
- Not much data available
- No antimicrobial resistance detected

Sustainability: Survey is alive and maintained.

Guide for accessing relevant data and models for quantitative microbial risk assessment

First picture of data (model, figure)

A living document for the guide can be achieved by:

- Versioning (f. ex. Zenodo)
- Living document

The guide is available online: <https://lguillier.quarto.pub/guide-data/>

Highlights: EFSA and ECDC data, FoodEX, IFSAC categorization schema, PIF

Source attribution

1. Validation of source attribution model
2. Criteria for strains to include in a scientific study for source attribution
 - a. Strains from sources (such as animal and food, but not from clinical animal samples)
 - b. Human strains (requirement of minimum of 100)
 - c. Other criteria

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-020-0417-7>

Can EJP CARE collection contribute to source attribution studies?

No. Among others, because we do not get enough strains from one source.

GWAS

Concept, definition of GWAS (statistical validation of genotype to phenotype match)

Other methods: machine learning, has the advantage that it can predict phenotype (GWAS cannot).

Can CARE strains contribute to that? Yes, especially for AMR (as a complement to existing databases). We could include strains from source attribution studies in OHEJP CARE.

Risk assessment

Genomic and quantitative risk assessment.

- EFSA BIOHAZ Panel (2019) was presented as an example.
- Sources of variability
- Strain variability
- Cold smoked salmon model as an example

From risk assessment we can draw conclusions like 12.6% exposure to salmon gives 97% of risk to Listeria. Could be useful for policy makers.
Not sure if CARE collection can contribute to genomic QMRA.

Remarks:

- It would be nice to have a panel of bacteria, f. ex Listeria strains for food producers. Based on that, they could test for these specific strains.
- Importance of keeping the collections alive and updated was stressed.
- Funding issue was brought up – how to do it after the project ends.
- The deadline for publishing in Frontiers has been extended until the end of December 2022. Rene encouraged everyone to submit.

Gap analysis proposition

Strategy 1: Follow the proportions observed in large or representative study.

Strategy 2: Ensure that you have the n subclass that represents 90 of all strains.

Reference studies for the gap analysis

Definition of the subtypes of interest (CC/ST, serovar, biotype)

Reference like ECDC TESSy would be good.

rStrainSelect

Representing and curating metadata of a strain collection

1. Create a metadata dictionary
2. Show repartition for each meta
3. Show interaction between metadata
 - a. Metadata_treemap
 - b. Metadata_sankeyplot
 - c. Metadata_upset

Illustrations of sampling strategies

Tackle complexity of metadata

Cluster sampling based on metadata

Meeting closure

Rene thanked all for actively participating in the workshops for the individual WP's during the closing meeting. EJP CARE activities will be ongoing the next months and deliverables finalized before the EJP project ends by 31 December 2022.

All partners and stakeholders will be invited for a virtual meeting in which WP leads will present the key outcomes of the project as well as future perspectives. This meeting will be on 2 December 2022 14-15:30.

Appendix:

- Meeting agenda

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This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. JIPs CARE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Final Meeting
OHEJP JIP CARE

Grant Agreement number 773830

September 21-22, 2022
Jernesalen, Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark

AGENDA

Attendees: Project Consortia (in person only)

<i>September 21</i>	
9.00-9.10	Arrival and welcome
9.10-9.30	Introduction to the meeting Rene S. Hendriksen (DTU, Denmark) and Mia Torpdahl (SSI, Denmark)
9.30-10.00	Presentation WP1 – Targets, accomplishments and sustainability. Set the scene for the workshop. Jeppe Boel (SSI, Denmark)
10.00-10.15	<i>Break</i>
10.15-12.00	WP1 Workshop – Development of new cross-sectorial PT/EQA's
12.00-12.30	WP1 reporting for DMP and 12 month report final year.
12.30-13.30	<i>Lunch</i>
13.30-14.00	Presentation WP2 and WP3 – Targets, accomplishments and sustainability. Set the scene for the workshop. Olivier Chesneau (IP, France) and Michel-Yes Mistou (INRAE, France)
14.00-15.00	WP2/3 Workshop What was done for Bacillus cereus and how will be conducted the gap analysis / Accessibility of the libraries of reference MALDI-ToF spectra
15.00-15.15	<i>Break</i>
15.15-16.00	WP2/3 Workshop (continued) – Strategy and proposals for ensuring the development of the CARE collection
16.00-16.30	WP2/3 reporting for DMP and 12 month report final year.
17.00-20.00	Social Dinner – Gorilla, Kødbyen
<i>September 22</i>	
9.00-09.30	Presentation WP4 – Targets, accomplishments and sustainability. Set the scene for the workshop. Laurent Guillier (ANSES, France)
9.30-10.15	WP4 Workshop – Definition of the relevance of the CARE strains for source attribution, risk assessment and GWAS studies
10.15-10.30	<i>Break</i>
10.30-11.30	WP4 Workshop – Example of application of the rSelectStrain tool: examples of use depending on the purpose of the study
11.30-12.00	WP4 reporting for DMP and 12 month report final year.
12.00-12.30	<i>Closure</i>

The meeting will not be recorded.